

Zenodo Access - User Agreement

Title: The SMART-VERTIGO database: Hand-held Smartphone-Based Eye-Video Dataset for Acute vertigo Diagnosis in Emergency Settings

Pseudo De-identified Eye Video Dataset

Dataset: Cropped and de-identified eye videos

Purpose: Research and public interest only

Host: Zenodo (restricted access)

Before downloading this dataset, you must acknowledge and agree to the following terms:

1. Access Eligibility

- I am a researcher or affiliated with a recognized academic or research institution.
- I will provide accurate institutional affiliation and contact information.

2. Permitted Use

- I will use this dataset **only for research purposes** and in ways that serve the **public interest**.
- I will **not use the dataset for commercial purposes** or redistribute it.
- I understand that I must **not attempt to re-identify individuals** from the dataset.

3. Data Description

- I acknowledge that the dataset contains **cropped and fully de-identified eye videos**, with all personal metadata, timestamps, or other identifiable information removed.
- I understand that the original consent covered general face video recording, but the cropped eye images **cannot reasonably be linked to any individual** and **do not constitute personal data under GDPR**.

4. Legal Compliance

- I will comply with all applicable **EU data protection laws**, including GDPR, where relevant.
- I acknowledge that the dataset has been curated in accordance with GDPR standards for scientific research (Articles 4, 5, 6, 9, 32, 89; Recitals 26, 33, 50, 156, 159).
- I will implement **appropriate technical and organizational measures** to prevent unauthorized access, disclosure, or misuse of the dataset.

5. Prohibited Actions

- I will not attempt to re-identify any individual in the dataset.
- I will not share the dataset with anyone not explicitly authorized.

- I will not use the dataset for purposes outside **research or public interest**.
- I will not use the dataset for commercial gain.
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6. Liability

- I understand that misuse of the dataset, including re-identification or unlawful processing, is **my responsibility** and may constitute a breach of GDPR or other laws.
- I acknowledge that the dataset provider assumes **no liability** for violations of this agreement by users.
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7. Agreement

By checking all boxes and submitting this form, I confirm that I:

- Understand the nature of the dataset and associated risks
- Agree to comply with all terms above
- Accept that access may be revoked if any term is violated

Full Name: _____

Institution: _____

Date: _____

[Submit and Confirm Agreement]